

Preparation of Jellies of some Inorganic Substances.

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In previous publications (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1926, **152**, 399; 1927, **164**, 63; 1927, **168**, 209) we have studied the conditions of the formation of jellies of vanadium pentoxide, ceric hydroxide and hydroxides of zirconium, ferric iron, aluminium and chromium.

In this paper, we have investigated the conditions of the formation of following jellies, which we are the first to obtain:

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|-------------------------|---------------------------|
| (i) Ferric borate. | (vii) Stannic arsenate. |
| (ii) Ferric molybdate. | (viii) Stannic phosphate. |
| (iii) Ferric tungstate. | (ix) Stannic tungstate. |
| (iv) Thorium arsenate. | (x) Stannic molybdate. |
| (v) Thorium phosphate. | (xi) Stannic borate. |
| (vi) Thorium molybdate. | |

Jelly formation with ferric, zinc, cadmium, copper and manganese arsenates has been reported by Grimaux (*Compt. rend.*, 1884, **98**, 1540), Coloriano (*Bull. Soc. Chim. France*, 1886, **45**, 711), Deiss (*Kolloid Z.*, 1914, **14**, 139), Holmes and co-workers (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, **38**, 1970; 1918, **40**, 1014; 1919, **41**, 763), Klemp and Gyulay (*Kolloid Z.*, 1918, **22**, 57; 1921, **23**, 262), Kraemer (*Colloid Symposium, Wisc.*, 1923, **1**, 61), Weiser (*ibid.*, 1923, **1**, 38) and others. No work seems to have been done before with jellies of borates, tungstates and molybdates.

Ferric molybdate jellies.

When potassium molybdate solution is added to a ferric chloride solution, a yellowish white precipitate is obtained, which dissolves on shaking, if ferric chloride is in excess. This clear mixture on standing for some time develops opalescence and finally, if concentrations are favourable, the whole mixture sets to a firm opaque jelly.

For preparation of these jellies 4 c.c. of $M/2.69$ -ferric chloride solution were taken in test tubes and varying amounts of 10% potassium molybdate solution were added, and the total volume in each case was made up to 10 c.c. by adding the requisite amount of water. The test tubes were well shaken after mixing the contents till clear solutions were obtained and then allowed to stand.

TABLE I.

Total volume = 10 c.c.

Ferric chloride.	Potassium molybdate, 10%.	Observations.
2 c.c.	1.5 c.c.	Solution becomes turbid but no jelly.
2	2.0	" " " "
2	2.5	Loose opaque jelly in 2 days with supernatant liquid.
2	3.0	Loose opaque jelly in 2 days with supernatant liquid.
4	3	No jelly.
4	3.5	Firm opaque jelly in 2 days.
4	4	Firm opaque jelly in a day.
4	5	Firm opaque jelly in a day.
5	5	Firm opaque jelly in a day.

Ferric borate jellies.

When a saturated solution of borax is added gradually to ferric chloride solution, a bulky precipitate occurs which goes on dissolving on shaking, but when sufficient quantity of borax has been added, the ferric borate settles down suddenly in the form of a bulky opaque jelly, which begins to synerise soon, and then it breaks up.

We have also obtained transparent ferric borate jelly by dialysing a mixture of 60 c.c. of ferric chloride ($M/2.69$) and 45 c.c. of 20% borax containing an excess of ferric chloride to peptise ferric borate. The clear red solution was allowed to dialyse for 30 days. The red sol thus obtained sets to a fine transparent red jelly on addition of potassium chloride or potassium sulphate.

TABLE II.

Concentration of the sol = 11.78 gm. ferric borate per litre.

Electrolyte. (c.c.)	Ferric borate. (c.c.)	Total volume. (c.c.)	Observation.
N-KCl 0.3	3.0	3.3	Instantaneously clear red gel; syneresis begins within 5 minutes.
N-KCl 0.2	3.0	3.2	Instantaneously clear red gel; syneresis soon.
N-KCl 0.4	3	3.4	Instantaneously sets up but immediately breaks up.
N-KI 0.1	3.0	3.1	„ „ „
N/10-KCl 0.3	3.0	3.3	Transparent gel in 2 minutes.
N/10-KCl 0.2	3.0	3.2	Transparent gel setting in 10 minutes; no syneresis.
N/10-KCl 0.1	3.0	3.1	Sets in 10 hours; no syneresis.
N-KCl 0.1	5.0	5.1	Instantly clear gel.
N/10-KCl 0.2	2.0	3.2	Transparent gel in 15 minutes; no syneresis in 2 days.
N/50-K ₂ SO ₄ 0.2	3.0	3.2	Transparent gel in 4 days; no syneresis in even 2 days.

In almost all the cases, syneresis soon begins: the greater the concentration of the electrolyte, the more rapid is the syneresis.

Thorium molybdate jelly.

When potassium molybdate solution is added to thorium nitrate, a white precipitate of thorium molybdate occurs, but if the mixture is vigorously shaken, this precipitate goes on dissolving till a clear viscous solution is obtained. On standing for some time, the whole mass sets to a transparent colourless jelly. These jellies are very stable and do not synerise and do not become turbid markedly on keeping for months.

5 C.c. of a solution of thorium nitrate containing 12.035 gm. in 250 c.c. were taken in test tubes and various amounts of 3% or 10% potassium molybdate were added and the solutions made up to 6 c.c. in each case. The mixtures were vigorously shaken for 5 minutes and the time for gelation was recorded.

TABLE III.

Total volume=6 c.c.

Thorium nitrate.	Potassium molybdate (3%).	Observation.
5 c.c.	1 c.c.	Transparent jelly in 5 hours with slight opalescence; stable.
5	0.8	Transparent jelly in 5½ hours.
5	0.6	Transparent jelly in 24 hours.
5	0.4	No jelly in a week.
5	0.2	" " "
5	0.5 (of 10 %)	Transparent jelly in 1 hour 8 mins.
5	1.0 (of 10 %)	Opaque jelly in 40 minutes, but breaks up in 12 days.
3	1	Transparent jelly within 22 hours, breaks up in 12 days.
3	0.6	Transparent jelly within 22 hours.

Thorium phosphate jellies.

No phosphate jellies have been prepared before without dialysis, by directly mixing the constituents of the reaction. Thorium phosphate jellies, which we have obtained, are prepared with the same ease as zinc and manganese arsenate jellies and these are perfectly transparent, firm and colourless and are very stable. Time of gelation can be extended to a very long period by varying the concentrations. The time of gelation in the cases of manganese and zinc arsenate jellies, however, could not be extended beyond 10-15 minutes.

5 C.c. of a solution of thorium nitrate (12.085 gm. in 250 c.c.) were taken in test tubes and varying amounts of potassium phosphate (22% solution) were added, keeping the total volume in all cases to 6 c.c. The mixtures were well shaken for 3 minutes and then allowed to stand. The nature of jelly and period of gelation were recorded.

TABLE IV.

Total volume = 6 c.c.

Thorium nitrate.	Potassium phosphate (22 %).	Observation.
5 c.c.	1 c.c.	Transparent jelly after 22 hours.
5	0.7	Transparent jelly after 78 hours.
5	0.5	Instantaneously white opaque jelly.
5	0.3	Transparent jelly in 15 minutes.
5	0.2	Transparent jelly in 4 hours.
3	0.3	Precipitated to a opaque jelly with supernatant liquid in 2 hours.
3	0.7	Transparent jelly after 22 hours.

Thorium arsenate jellies.

These jellies resemble manganese and zinc arsenate jellies in their mode of preparation but differ from them in being slightly turbid, and also in the fact that these require much higher concentration of arsenate solution for preparation. When to thorium nitrate solution a few drops of potassium arsenate solution are added, gelatinous precipitate appears which dissolves on shaking and finally the whole mass sets to a firm jelly. These arsenate jellies are either translucent or opaque and their opacity increases with time on standing. A slight syneresis appears to begin just after their formation but it does not proceed far. These jellies are quite stable and hard.

5 C.c. of a solution of thorium nitrate (12.035 gm. in 250 c.c.) were taken in test tubes and various amounts of potassium arsenate (45 gm. in 250 c.c.) solution were added to it and the mixture was shaken for 2 minutes. The total volume in each case was kept to be 6 c.c.

TABLE V.

Total volume = 6 c.c.

Thorium nitrate.	Potassium arsenate.	Observation.
5 c.c.	0.25 c.c.	Translucent jelly after 22 hours.
5	0.30	Translucent jelly in 1 hour.
5	0.40	Translucent jelly in 5 minutes.
5	0.50	Translucent jelly in 1 minute; a slight syneresis soon begins.
5	1.0	Instantaneously, white opaque jelly.
5	0.15	No jelly but white precipitate in 10 days.
3	0.4	Translucent jelly setting in 1 minute.
3	0.3	Translucent jelly in 45 minutes.

Stannic arsenate jellies.

Stannic chloride solution, when mixed with potassium arsenate solution, gives the precipitate of stannic arsenate ; but if stannic chloride be in excess, this precipitate dissolves and a clear colourless solution is obtained. In these solutions, opalescence begins within five minutes and finally stable jellies are obtained provided the concentrations are favourable. These jellies are almost transparent with very slight opalescence in the beginning when freshly formed, but opacity increases with time and finally they become white and opaque. Opacity also increases with the concentration of potassium arsenate solution used.

To 2 or 3 c.c. of $M/1\cdot099$ -stannic chloride solution, varying concentrations of potassium arsenate solution (45 gm. in 250 c.c.) are mixed and the volume is kept constant. The following are the observations when jellies were allowed to set at the room temperature (18-20°).

TABLE VI.

Total volume = 6 c.c.

Stannic chloride.	Potassium arsenate.	Observation.
3 c.c.	3 c.c.	Transparent jelly in 25 minutes ; becomes opalescent and finally opaque.
3	2	Sets to a transparent jelly in $1\frac{1}{2}$ hour.
3	1	Opaque jelly within 23 hours.
2	4	Sets to opaque white firm jelly in 2 minutes.
2	3	Sets to translucent jelly in 5 minutes.
2	2	Sets to translucent jelly in 6 minutes.
2	0·5	Sets to opaque jelly in 24 hours.
1	1·0	Sets to translucent jelly in 2 minutes.

It has been observed that greater the concentration of stannic chloride, the more will be the transparency of the freshly formed jelly. Undoubtedly all jellies become equally opaque on standing for a long time.

The process of gelation is greatly accelerated by raising the temperature, though the jellies formed at higher temperatures are more opaque and perhaps less fine in texture. The results recorded in the

following table are of the same jellies of same concentration as the above except that these have been warmed for 5 minutes in a bath of constant temperature of 90°.

TABLE VII.

Total volume=6 c.c.

Stannic chloride.	Potassium arsenate.	Observation.
3 c.c.	3 c.c.	Sets in 3 minutes to opaque jelly.
3	2	Sets in 6 minutes to opaque jelly.
3	1	Sets in 10 hours to opaque jelly.
3	0.5	Highly viscous liquid but does not set even in 10 days.
2.0	0.5	Sets to loose opaque jelly in 5 minutes.

Stannic phosphate jelly.

Stannic phosphate jelly has been obtained in the same way as stannic arsenate. When potassium phosphate (KH_2PO_4) is added to stannic chloride solution, stannic phosphate is precipitated and under favourable concentrations, even transparent jellies are obtained which are mostly accompanied with very slight opalescence. The jellies, however, become quite opaque within a few hours after setting. 3 C.c. of stannic chloride ($M/1.099$) solution were taken in test tubes and various amounts of potassium phosphate solutions (55 gm. in 250 c.c.) were added, and the total volume was made up to 6 c.c. in every case.

TABLE VIII.

Total volume=6 c.c.

Stannic chloride.	Potassium phosphate.	Observation.
3 c.c.	3 c.c.	Sets in 15 minutes to translucent firm jelly.
3	2	Sets in 18 minutes to translucent firm jelly.
3	1.5	Sets in 30 minutes to „ „
3	1.0	Sets in 2 hours „ „
3	0.5	Sets to jelly in 22 hours.
2	2	Sets in 4*minutes to opaque jelly.
2	1	Sets to transparent jelly in 7 minutes.
1	0.5	Sets in 2 minutes to white opaque jelly.

All these jellies, though differ initially in their transparency, become opaque after keeping for a few days. These are very stable and hard and do not exhibit any marked syneresis. The speed of gelation is much accelerated by allowing them to set at higher temperatures. The following table records the observations taken at 90°. 3 C.c. of stannic chloride ($M/1.099$) solution, mixed with various amounts of potassium phosphate solution, were warmed in a bath of constant temperature at 90°, and the time of setting was noted. All jellies formed at this temperature are mostly opaque from the beginning of formation and are quite stable and hard and do not undergo any marked syneresis.

TABLE IX.

Total volume = 6 c.c.

Stannic chloride.	Potassium phosphate.	Observation.
3 c.c.	2 c.c.	Sets to translucent jelly in 1 minute.
3	1.5	Sets to opaque jelly in 2 minutes.
3	1.0	Sets to opaque jelly in 3 minutes.
3	0.5	Sets to opaque jelly in 5 minutes.

Stannic tungstate jellies.

We have also prepared stannic tungstate jellies. 1.5 or 2 c.c. of stannic chloride solution ($1.59 M$) were taken in test tubes and to them various amounts of 15% sodium tungstate solution were added and the total volume was always made up to 6 c.c. Each mixture was thoroughly shaken for 5 minutes, when a turbid solution was obtained. The solution became quite clear after keeping for another 10 minutes. After some period, which differs according to the concentration of sodium tungstate, slight opalescence begins which intensifies and finally an opaque jelly is obtained.

TABLE X.

Total volume = 6 c.c.

Stannic chloride.	Sodium tungstate.	Observation.
2 c.c.	2 c.c.	Opalescent solution, no jelly.
2	2.50	Opalescent solution, no jelly.
2	3	Sets to opaque firm jelly in 5 days.
2	3.5	Sets to opaque firm jelly in 2 days.
2	4	Sets to opaque firm jelly in 12 hrs.
1.5	4	Sets to opaque firm jelly in 1½ hrs.
1.5	3.5	Sets to opaque firm jelly in 3 hrs.

All these jellies are opaque, white, hard and stable and do not undergo any marked syneresis. The gelation in this case is also accelerated if setting is done at a higher temperature. 2 C.c. of stannic chloride solution (1.53M) were mixed with various amounts of 15% sodium tungstate and the mixture was shaken for 5 minutes and then warmed in a bath at 93° till the contents set to jelly.

TABLE XI.

Total volume = 6 c.c.

Stannic chloride.	Sodium tungstate.	Observation.
2 c.c.	2 c.c.	Warmed for 20 minutes but no jelly; only white turbid solution obtained.
2	2.5	Sets in 20 minutes to white opaque jelly.
2	3.0	Sets in 8 minutes to opaque jelly.
2	3.5	Sets in 6 minutes to opaque jelly.
1.5	2	Sets in 8 minutes to opaque jelly.

A slight syneresis appears when jellies are transferred from the bath to room temperature (19°) but the syneresis does not proceed any further. Jellies prepared in the hot are also quite stable and hard.

Stannic borate jellies.

When a saturated borax solution obtained at 90° is added to 1.5 M-stannic chloride solution, a white precipitate of stannic borate is formed which dissolves on shaking. If suitable concentrations are chosen and the mixture is warmed at 90°-95°, loose white opaque jelly is obtained which breaks up in a short time. If stannic chloride solution contains much free hydrochloric acid, which is always associated with hydrated stannic chlorides, stannic borate does not set even on warming.

To 1.5M-stannic chloride solution, a saturated borax solution is added and the mixture containing an excess of stannic chloride was dialysed for 24 hours; a clear transparent sol was obtained, which sets to transparent jellies on addition of electrolytes like potassium chloride or sulphate. The sol itself becomes more and more viscous even without the addition of electrolytes and sets within 24 hours.

TABLE XII.

Concentration of sol = 66.40 gm. SnO_2 per litre.
Sol taken = 2 c.c. Total volume = 4 c.c.

Electrolyte.

<i>N</i> /15- K_2SO_4	0.5 c.c.	Firm opaque jelly in half-minute.
	0.3	Translucent jelly in 2 minutes.
	0.1	Transparent jelly with slight opalescence in 5 minutes.
	0.05	Transparent jelly with slight opalescence in 7 minutes.
<i>N</i> /5-KCl	1.0	Transparent jelly in 6 minutes.
	0.5	Transparent jelly within 8 minutes.
	0.3	Transparent jelly in 10 minutes.
	0.1	Transparent jelly in 15 minutes.

These jellies are transparent at the time of formation, but opalescence soon develops and finally white and opaque jellies are formed. These jellies are quite firm and stable and do not show any marked syneresis.

Stannic molybdate jellies.

No jelly has been obtained by directly mixing the solutions of potassium molybdate and stannic chloride, whereby a white precipitate of gelatinous nature is only formed. However, if potassium molybdate (15% solution) be added below precipitation value to stannic chloride solution, and the mixture be allowed to dialyse for 24 hours, a clear sol with slight opalescence is obtained. The sol obtained contained 91.04 gm. of SnO_2 per litre. The sol is fairly stable and does not set to jelly without addition of electrolytes, but if it is half-diluted, it sets to a white translucent firm jelly within 6 hours. It appears to be stabilised in presence of potassium chloride though jellies are readily formed in presence of potassium sulphate, as is seen in the following table.

TABLE XIII.

Total volume = 4 c. c.

Tin molybdate sol.	Electrolyte,	
2 c.c.	<i>N</i> /5- K_2SO_4	1.5 c.c.
2	1.0	Translucent jellies in 6 hours.
2	0.5	White opaque jelly in 2 minutes.
2	0.2	White translucent jelly in 30 mins.
2	0.1	" " " 75 "
2	0.5	Translucent jelly in 1½ hours.
2	0.3	" " " 3 "
1		Loose " opaque jelly in " 5 minutes,
		syneresis soon begins.
1	0.1	Firm opaque jelly in 5 minutes.
1	0.05	" " " 20 "
2	<i>N</i> /1-KCl	0.4
2	1.0	" " " 40 "
2	2.0	Translucent jelly in 2 days.
		" " " " "
		No jelly in 3 days.

Like other stannic jellies, these are almost transparent when freshly formed but become opaque on keeping for some time. Effect of temperature on formation of these jellies is also quite appreciable: the process of gelation appears to be accelerated by the rise in temperature. To 2 c.c. of the above sol, 2 c.c. of water are added and the time of gelation is noted at different temperatures.

TABLE XIV.

Temperature	90°	70°	60°	50°	40°	24°
Time of gelation (in mins.)	1	2	4	7	20	360
Translucent jelly in all cases.						

Ferric tungstate jellies.

When 15% solution of sodium tungstate is added to *M/2*-ferric chloride solution, a bulky precipitate is formed which dissolves to some extent on vigorous shaking but if the mixture is warmed in a water-bath at 96° for 5 minutes, it is completely dissolved and a clear transparent yellow solution is obtained, which sets to a fine yellow, opaque jelly when the concentrations are suitable.

TABLE XV.

The mixture has been warmed for 5 minutes at 95° in all cases. Total volume = 5 c.c.

<i>M/2</i> Ferric chloride. 2 c.c.	Sodium tungstate (15%). 3 c.c.	
2	2.5	Yellow opaque jelly within 20 hours.
2	2.0	" " "
2	2.0	Yellow opaque jelly in 2 days.
1.5	3.5	Bulky opaque yellow jelly in 3 minutes.
1.5	3.0	" " 5 "
1.5	2.5	Fine opaque yellow jelly in 5 minutes.
1.5	2.0	" " 2 days.
1.5	1.5	No jelly in 3 days.

These jellies resemble ferric molybdate jellies. Opaque, yellow ferric arsenate and phosphate jellies are also obtained if suitable amount of potassium arsenate or phosphate solutions are added to ferric chloride solutions. However, so long as ferric chloride is

much in excess to peptise ferric arsenate and phosphate, clear red sols are obtained which give beautiful transparent jellies on dialysis as prepared by Holmes and co-workers. In the case of tungstate and molybdate, no red sols are obtained on mixing ferric chloride and sodium tungstate or potassium molybdate and as such, on dialysis, these mixtures do not give transparent jellies.

Further work on jelly formation is in progress in these laboratories.

Summary.

The following inorganic jellies have been obtained for the first time and their method of preparation described :—

(1) Ferric borate, (2) ferric molybdate, (3) ferric tungstate, (4) thorium arsenate, (5) thorium phosphate, (6) thorium molybdate, (7) stannic arsenate, (8) stannic phosphate, (9) stannic tungstate, (10) stannic molybdate, and (11) stannic borate.

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Received May 13, 1929.